

**INTEGRATING SPEAKING AND LISTENING SKILLS TO IMPROVE
LANGUAGE COMPREHENSION AMONG YOUNG LEARNERS****Gulmira Ismoilova***student at Karshi State University***Abstract**

Many teachers have a difficulty in teaching young learners because of their age and comprehension limitations, so using integrated approach can be effective for both teachers and students to improve language learning efficiency. Choosing appropriate material can increase language acquisition among youngsters and make lessons more interesting than traditional classes. Listening and speaking are the main skills to communicate and improve students' comprehension that is why it becomes popular among teachers to combine them during the classes. This article reflects on how to improve young learners' oral communication, make classes more energetic and increase language learning productivity when speaking and listening skills are taught in an integrated way.

From the age point of young learners, they get easily distracted. To focus their attention and improve language acquisition, teachers can use an approach – teaching speaking and listening skills in an integrated way. This paper contributes to the field of teaching and the aim of this study is to give detailed information about what is the speaking skill, as well as deals with the issues of listening skills, how to integrate these skills to help young learners' comprehension and provide useful information in choosing materials to use on this approach. Prior studies have found that integrating these skills are essential in effective communication and helps learners to express themselves confidently despite some limitations of this approach. Although the majority of teachers moved to modern teaching methods, in Uzbekistan many teachers still use traditional methods of teaching in schools and that is why according to statistics Uzbekistan remains one of the countries with low English proficiency. In order to alleviate this problem, I choose this topic and make it clearer and easier than this matter has been researched in previous works.

It is generally accepted knowledge that four skills: reading, listening, writing and speaking are the main fundamentals of communicating and understanding someone, especially, speaking and listening are crucial skills for learners to acquire. They are essential in effective communication and help learners express themselves clearly and confidently. Therefore, it is essential for language educators to equip learners with necessary speaking and listening skills that can enable them to speak and listen effectively in various contexts. As Foote cited – “Listening and

speaking are, regardless of who the people using the language are, at least as important as the other skills to communicate” []. In their work Freeman and Richards agreed with the statement given above, as they deeply grasp that “these two skills are core to communicate” []. One should keep in mind that these skills are normally integrated in real life. During communication people listen foreign speech and it will be much clearer in concrete situation and surely will be integrated by speaking. Blanka Frydrychova Klimova mentioned that “listening is usually an interactive process”[]. We clearly know that listener does not always just listen to someone, but she or he also comment to the speaker or asks questions for clarification. The most essential issue for the learners should be to understand what they are listening to and to be able to give appropriate responses orally. This goal brings us to the integration of listening and speaking while teaching, as our main consideration should be not only learning the grammar of the target language but also communicating in that language, which highlights the importance of the integration of these two skills. These two skills should be taught in integration to guide learners to develop their oral communicative competencies Speaking and listening are two crucial communication skills that are interconnected and complementary to each other. The importance of speaking and listening in an integrated way can be seen in the following ways: When we listen carefully, we are more likely to understand the speaker's message accurately. When we speak, we ensure that our message is clear, concise, and easily comprehensible for our audience. Together, these skills promote improved understanding in communication. Effective speaking and listening also contribute to building stronger relationships. When people feel heard and understood, they are more likely to trust and connect to each other. Active listening and clear speaking skills can help resolve conflicts by ensuring that each party understands the other's perspective and works towards a mutually beneficial solution.

Supporting students with their speaking and listening skills can be foundation on their further literacy development. As LervAag, Hulme, & Melby-Lervag indicates that “speaking and listening can predict later literacy success” []. Age of the students is leading cause of the trouble that they have limited abilities to learn something and it is considered for their specific features. It is difficult to say when it started to analyze young learners but it is obvious that teaching and learning foreign languages became a trend over the whole world. There are different points of view about the age of the young learners. For instance, Anna Maria Pinter divides young learners to 3 groups: “First group is pre-chool children who is considered up to 3 age and second one is children who start primary school between 5 and 7. And the last group is children who finish primary school around 13 and 15” []. But, Lyna Cameron considered young learners' age between five and twelve []. Of course, every contry's school age differ from each other that is

why, considering many researchers' points of view, it can be concluded that ages from 3 to 13 can be the best match for the young learners for every nation. Surely, it cannot be taught all young learners the same way, since every age has their own language learning abilities. For this reason, scientists divide young learners to 2 groups: "very young learner from 3 to 7 and young learners from 8 to 13" [].

There are many young children's specific features to take into consideration while teaching young learners. First of all they are energetic and they can easily get bored from conventional classes that teacher takes main role instead of students, so teacher should grab and hold their attention and it is not easy as it is said. And indeed, their literacy abilities are really poor and trying to teach them with methods such as grammar-translation can be boring, difficult, takes more time even students can spend the whole class-hour just for writing and eventually, it can reduce students' interest in learning languages. Their brains also cannot take the storm of information and their memories are short-termed that means they cannot remember data for a long time, especially incomprehensible information. According to Andreas Puskas: "In order to maximize learning and provide support and challenge in learning, it is crucial for the teacher to be well-informed about the learner. It is vital to have information about the physical, emotional, conceptual and educational characteristics of the young learner and consider certain issues and views on how children think and learn". [] In this point to develop students' comprehension integrating speaking and listening skills can be helpful. When teachers show students topic-related videos or play audios students can easily focus their attention on the class and at the second time they will repeat audios that help pupils to fulfill their vocabulary basis and learn how to pronounce it instead of drilling with teachers.

As Hinkel mentioned, "In the context of real and meaningful communication, one typically needs to listen and comprehend L2 speech and speak at a very fast pace". [] That is, both bottom-up and top-down language processing are required. The terms top-down and bottom-up were explained by Eli Hinkel Seattle Pacific University: "The term *bottom-up processing* refers to trying to comprehend what is said or written by focusing on incremental elements of language, such as basic units of sounds, words, or grammar. The term *top-down processing* refers to focusing on broad matters of language, such as the topic, background knowledge and information, and the context." []

Course-books, particularly primary school course-books focus on basic listening and speaking exercises so that teachers may not have a difficulty to find out appropriate materials to connect skills when teaching learners. But using authentic materials can be beneficial to learners to use second language in real-life situations. In that case, there are a number of points to take into

consideration when choosing material to integrate speaking and listening in young learners – like students’ age and level, students’ interest, students’ literacy comprehension, usefulness of the material and etc. Safaroglu and Uzakgore mentioned in their work that “listening needs to be given regular attention during lessons, so by breaking down activities into tangible chunks, teachers can slowly help learners develop their ear, and by using authentic materials as the basis for the activity, learners are exposed to ‘real English’”. [] A quick way of gaining early fluency in a language is to memorize useful phrases. There are several advantages in doing this. First, simple communication can occur at an early stage. For example, learners should be able to say who they are, where they come from, and what they do from the very first language lessons. According to this view, it can be understood that young learners cannot take a huge storm of information and they cannot improve their listening skills with only one listening activity instead of this teachers should use jigsaw method that help them improve listening comprehension on a daily basis. Like listening, speaking also can be improved just by repeating listened activities, music and rhythms. And every lesson should be connected to each other to practice previous lessons and connect them on a daily basis help students to be able to use second language.

As with any instructional approach, there may be potential drawback to the integration of speaking and listening skills in language education. While it is widely accepted that an integrated approach is effective in language learning, it is also important to recognize that there may be challenges that result from this integration. When teachers use integrated approach some students may feel overwhelmed and they always need support from their teachers, especially young learners. In slideplayer site it is mentioned that ‘integrating speaking and listening is that learners may struggle to understand and respond appropriately to native speakers of the target language’. This can be especially problematic if learners are only exposed to classroom instruction and have limited opportunities to interact with native speakers. Despite the limitations, instructors must acknowledge the importance of integrating speaking and listening skills in language education. It aids learners in developing their communicative abilities in a second language and reflects an essential component of language proficiency. To address the challenges of integrating speaking and listening effectively, considerations such as group proficiencies, classroom management, cultural interests, and technology integration.

On this basis, we conclude that language learning is an intricate process that involves learning four key skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Of these four skills, listening and speaking are perhaps the most fundamental as they are used for communication, the ultimate goal of language learning. Teaching listening and speaking activities as an integrated aspect of second language acquisition is crucial for enhancing the linguistic abilities of language learners.

This requires a holistic approach where listening and speaking activities are integrated into all aspects of language learning. The integration of listening and speaking activities into the language curriculum is not a new concept. However, it is often an aspect of language learning that is neglected or is left without a clear emphasis. Teaching listening and speaking skills in isolation can lead to an indecisive and stilted learning experience for language learners. This is because the skills needed for effective communication cannot be developed in isolation. Integrating speaking and listening can be beneficial for both teachers and students equally, despite some drawbacks. Additionally, young learners' age and level cannot be problem if teachers can choose appropriate materials according to above given aspects. In the future work, investigating vocabulary and pronunciation benefits in teaching speaking and listening in an integrated way might prove importance of this approach.

References

1. Seferoğlu and Uzakgöre, listening and speaking parts of english, 2004
2. Hinkel, E. (2006). Current perspectives on teaching the four skills. TESOL Quarterly, 40(1), 109–31
3. Andrea Puskás The Challenges and Practices of Teaching Young Learners Komárno, 2016. ISBN 978-80-8122-178-1
4. Lervåg, A., Hulme, C. and Melby-Lervåg, M. (2018), Unpicking the Developmental Relationship Between Oral Language Skills and Reading Comprehension: It's Simple, But Complex. Child Dev, 89: 1821–1838. doi:10.1111/cdev.12861
5. <https://www.diva-portal.org>
6. Blanka Frydrychova Klimova / Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 2014
7. <vvs://slideplayer.com/>
8. Bailey The language learner's autobiography: Examining the 'apprenticeship of observation'. In D. Freeman & J.C. Richards, Teacher learning in language teaching. New York: Cambridge.